

Partial molal volumes and expansibilities of some amino acids in aqueous solutions

Tarlok S. Banipal* and Parveen Kapoor

Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar-143 005, India

Manuscript received 17 November 1998, revised 24 May 1999, accepted 25 May 1999

Partial molal volumes ($\bar{V}_2^0$) at infinite dilution of glycine, DL-alanine, β -alanine, DL- α -amino-n-butyric acid, L-valine, L-leucine, L-isoleucine, L-phenylalanine, L-serine, L-threonine, L-proline and L-glutamic acid have been determined by density measurements using pycnometer at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K. These data in conjunction with the reported values at other temperatures have been utilized to estimate the precise partial molal expansibilities $(\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_P$ at infinite dilution and the values of $(\partial^2\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_P$ by different procedures. These parameters have been used to predict the structural hydration effects, i.e. the structure-making and structure-breaking effects of solutes in solutions. The precise values of $(\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_P$ have been used to convert the partial molal adiabatic compressibilities of the studied solutes to partial molal isothermal compressibilities at infinite dilution which is an ideal parameter for interpreting the results.

Amino acids and peptides are the fundamental structural units of proteins and thermodynamic properties of these model compounds in aqueous medium provide information about solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions which in turn help to understand several biochemical processes such as protein hydration, denaturation, aggregation etc.¹⁻¹⁴. Recent studies¹⁵⁻¹⁷ indicate that some classes of organisms exist in submarine hot springs at temperatures even higher than 383.15 K. Thus, the investigations of the thermodynamic properties of aqueous solutions of biological macromolecules, i.e. protein systems as a function of temperature and pressure are needed to understand the ability of these organisms to exist in such a hostile environment.

Partial molal volume ($\bar{V}_2^0$) is a useful property which provides information on solute-solvent interactions, however, its temperature-dependence may still be more useful in characterizing the structural hydration effects as the intrinsic volume of the solute is almost independent of temperature^{18,19}. Several workers have reported important volumetric data on amino acids in aqueous medium but most of the data have been determined at 298.15 K. Although some reports^{4,14,16,20-22} are available on volumetric data as a function of temperature but wide disagreement exists between the values of partial molal expansibilities, because the evaluation of reliable partial molal expansibility $(\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_P$ needs $\bar{V}_2^0$ values at large number of temperatures^{18,23}. Consequently, in order to have precise values of these parameters, we report partial molal volumes of glycine, DL-alanine, β -alanine, DL- α -amino-n-butyric acid, L-valine, L-leucine, L-isoleucine, L-phenylalanine, L-serine, L-threonine, L-proline and L-glutamic acid, determined from density measurements using pycnometer at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K. These

data in conjunction with that reported in literature have been utilized in estimating precise values of $(\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_P$ and $(\partial^2\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_P$ by different methods. This information has been used in predicting the hydration effects, i.e. structure-making and structure-breaking effects of solutes and in deriving the partial molal isothermal compressibilities $(K_{T,2}^0)$ from partial molal adiabatic compressibilities $(K_{S,2}^0)$.

Results and Discussion

Partial molal volumes ($\bar{V}_2^0$): Apparent molal volumes (ϕ_v) of various amino acids in water have been determined from density measurements using the relation,

$$\phi_v = \frac{M_2}{d} - \frac{(d-d_0)1000}{mdd_0} \quad (1)$$

where d and d_0 are the densities of solution and solvent respectively, m is the molality of the solute in the solvent and M_2 the molecular weight of the solute. ϕ_v values of amino acids at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K along with densities are given in Table 1 as a function of molality. Over the concentration range studied, ϕ_v is a linear function of molality, hence, partial molal volume at infinite dilution ($\bar{V}_2^0$) has been calculated by least-squares method using the relation,

$$\phi_v = \bar{V}_2^0 + S_v m \quad (2)$$

where S_v is the experimental slope. $\bar{V}_2^0$ and S_v values along with standard deviations are given in Table 2. Literature values^{4,10,11,16,17,20-22,28-31} wherever available are also included in Table 2 for comparison. As mentioned earlier, most of the data are available at 298.15 K and the present values are in good agreement with the literature values. At 308.15 K, values are available only for glycine and DL-

alanine^{4,22,29} and these are in good agreement with ours and values are not available at 318.15 K for comparison. From

Table-1 (contd.)

Table I. Density (<i>d</i>) and apparent molal volume (ϕ_v) of some amino acids at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K					
<i>m</i>	<i>d</i>	ϕ_v	<i>m</i>	<i>d</i>	ϕ_v
mol kg ⁻¹	g cm ⁻³	cm ³ mol ⁻¹	mol kg ⁻¹	g cm ⁻³	cm ³ mol ⁻¹
298.15 K					
Glycine					
0.06064	0.99897	43.30	0.09095	0.99993	43.34
0.12549	1.00102	43.42	0.15047	1.00179	43.40
0.19017	1.00302	43.45	0.23596	1.00443	43.48
0.26289	1.00524	43.55	0.27114	1.00549	43.58
0.31189	1.00674	43.60			
DL-Alanine					
0.02047	0.99763	60.58	0.05004	0.99848	60.50
0.07009	0.99905	60.52	0.09021	0.99962	60.54
0.12022	1.00046	60.56	0.14992	1.00129	60.59
0.16970	1.00185	60.60	0.20987	1.00296	60.67
0.25935	1.00433	60.68	0.29947	1.00542	60.72
0.32972	1.00623	60.77	0.37965	1.00759	60.78
β -Alanine					
0.05518	0.99874	58.39	0.09986	1.00009	58.48
0.15018	1.00162	58.47	0.18031	1.00251	58.56
0.22011	1.00369	58.58	0.27039	1.00519	58.59
0.30021	1.00606	58.61			
DL- α -Amino-n-butyric acid					
0.06828	0.99886	76.49	0.07596	0.99907	76.51
0.08370	0.99927	76.50	0.08762	0.99937	76.62
0.17612	1.00165	76.77	0.18477	1.00187	76.78
0.20215	1.00231	76.79	0.24981	1.00370	76.92
L-Valine					
0.05781	0.99856	91.07	0.07005	0.99886	91.20
0.08131	0.99915	91.17	0.08738	0.99931	91.19
0.11429	0.99998	91.30	0.12228	1.00019	91.33
0.13471	1.00051	91.27	0.14340	1.00073	91.31
0.15472	1.00102	91.38	0.16269	1.00120	91.38
0.18004	1.00163	91.41	0.19037	1.00188	91.47
0.21782	1.00256	91.50			
L-Leucine					
0.02239	0.99757	107.87	0.02731	0.99769	107.79
0.02843	0.99771	107.90	0.03487	0.99786	107.86
0.04405	0.99808	107.96	0.05463	0.99832	107.97
0.06415	0.99853	108.12	0.07028	0.99867	108.12
0.09667	0.99927	108.21	0.14405	1.00034	108.26
L-Isoleucine					
0.04652	0.99823	105.84	0.05426	0.99845	105.83
0.06637	0.99872	105.98	0.07332	0.99891	105.85
0.08092	0.99909	105.93	0.08472	0.99918	105.96
0.09305	0.99940	105.88	0.09852	0.99952	106.02
0.12665	1.00023	105.95			
L-Phenylalanine					
0.00944	0.99746	121.36	0.01506	0.99771	121.41
0.02001	0.99794	121.47	0.02277	0.99805	121.38
0.02493	0.99814	121.46	0.03091	0.99840	121.44
0.03485	0.99857	121.52			
L-Serine					
0.06844	1.00008	60.66	0.10981	1.00189	60.70
0.14949	1.00363	60.68	0.19973	1.00580	60.77
0.25008	1.00797	60.79	0.29609	1.00994	60.80
0.34024	1.01180	60.87			
L-Threonine					
0.06985	0.99998	76.92	0.09061	1.00085	76.98
0.15004	1.00331	77.00	0.19784	1.00526	77.05
0.23005	1.00657	77.09	0.25224	1.00746	77.12
0.28984	1.00899	77.11			
L-Proline					
0.04498	0.99851	82.63	0.06193	0.99905	82.78
0.08897	0.99992	82.67	0.09839	1.00022	82.77
0.10108	1.00031	82.71	0.14995	1.00185	82.83
0.22376	1.00416	82.89	0.26987	1.00557	82.95
0.28943	1.00615	83.02			
L-Glutamic acid					
0.03205	0.99888	89.73	0.03914	0.99928	89.91
0.04529	0.99963	89.88	0.05901	1.00041	89.98
0.06398	1.00068	90.00	0.08731	1.00199	90.07
308.15 K					
Glycine					
0.03237	0.99504	43.81	0.05059	0.99561	43.83
0.08073	0.99655	43.86	0.11096	0.99748	43.88
0.13040	0.99808	43.90	0.16283	0.99908	43.92
0.20051	1.00023	43.96	0.23278	1.00121	43.98
0.27291	1.00241	44.08	0.34268	1.00453	44.07
0.36697	1.00525	44.09	0.39539	1.00609	44.12
DL-Alanine					
0.02011	0.99460	61.02	0.05013	0.99544	61.05
0.07981	0.99627	61.08	0.11017	0.99712	61.11
0.14962	0.99821	61.14	0.19954	0.99957	61.19
0.25039	1.00095	61.23	0.30332	1.00238	61.26
0.33316	1.00318	61.28			
β -Alanine					
0.05513	0.99570	58.90	0.09987	0.99704	58.97
0.15277	0.99861	59.00	0.18197	0.99947	59.00
0.21795	1.00053	59.07	0.23977	1.00116	59.10
0.26201	1.00181	59.12			
DL- α -Amino-n-butyric acid					
0.06123	0.99966	76.71	0.07478	0.99601	76.78
0.08163	0.99619	76.73	0.12996	0.99745	76.81
0.15317	0.99804	76.95	0.17571	0.99862	76.94
0.19136	0.99902	76.96	0.19764	0.99917	77.00
0.21018	0.99951	76.92			
L-Valine					
0.04761	0.99526	91.60	0.07179	0.99587	91.68
0.09612	0.99648	91.73	0.13255	0.99741	91.72
0.15117	0.99787	91.77	0.18219	0.99863	91.81
0.21389	0.99940	91.90			
L-Leucine					
0.05146	0.99522	108.52	0.07215	0.99569	108.57
0.08753	0.99604	108.54	0.09817	0.99627	108.61
0.11915	0.99675	108.64	0.13514	0.99709	108.69
0.14037	0.99722	108.68			
L-Isoleucine					
0.04692	0.99521	106.52	0.07106	0.99579	106.70
0.09018	0.99626	106.70	0.10472	0.99662	106.73
0.11836	0.99695	106.75	0.13095	0.99725	106.74
0.14395	0.99756	106.80			
L-Phenylalanine					
0.00718	0.99434	122.91	0.01078	0.99449	122.94
0.01800	0.99480	122.97	0.02163	0.99495	123.02
0.02529	0.99511	123.08	0.02895	0.99526	123.13
0.03260	0.99541	123.16			

Banipal *et al.* : Partial molal volumes and expansibilities of some amino acids in aqueous solutions

Table-1 (contd.)

Table-1 (contd.)

L-Serine						0.13554	0.99324	109.59	0.14267	0.99339	109.60
0.05067	0.99625	61.20	0.07514	0.99732	61.21	0.14987	0.99355	109.62			
0.11304	0.99897	61.24	0.13475	0.99991	61.24						
0.16485	1.00019	61.28	0.18405	1.00202	61.30						
0.20886	1.00308	61.33									
L-Threonine											
0.06217	0.99662	77.56	0.09357	0.99791	77.60	0.04728	0.99139	107.48	0.07266	0.99201	107.47
0.13365	0.99955	77.59	0.15689	1.00049	77.65	0.07906	0.99217	107.48	0.09184	0.99247	107.48
0.21223	1.00273	77.70	0.22989	1.00343	77.72	0.11119	0.99294	107.51	0.11788	0.99309	107.56
0.25061	1.00425	77.76				0.13069	0.99339	107.54	0.15051	0.99386	107.60
L-Proline						0.16333	0.99417	107.54	0.17612	0.99447	107.53
0.05122	0.99567	83.15	0.07345	0.99638	83.22	0.19641	0.99494	107.62			
0.09198	0.99697	83.23	0.11072	0.99756	83.28						
0.13327	0.99826	83.32	0.18241	0.99979	83.37						
0.20913	1.00061	83.40									
L-Glutamic acid											
0.04078	0.99633	90.70	0.06544	0.99775	90.73						
0.09027	0.99909	90.79	0.11248	1.00032	90.84						
0.12086	1.00078	90.87	0.13479	1.00155	90.88						
0.14607	1.00216	90.93									
318.15 K											
Glycine											
0.04995	0.99178	44.24	0.06001	0.99209	44.26						
0.07525	0.99256	44.34	0.08026	0.99271	44.33						
0.09033	0.99302	44.33	0.10559	0.99348	44.37						
0.11069	0.99364	44.38	0.13105	0.99426	44.41						
0.14636	0.99472	44.43	0.16682	0.99534	44.45						
0.18042	0.99574	44.50	0.19163	0.99607	44.51						
DL-Alanine											
0.06098	0.99194	61.48	0.08325	0.99256	61.47						
0.09451	0.99287	61.50	0.11142	0.99333	61.53						
0.13403	0.99395	61.56	0.15708	0.99456	61.65						
0.17147	0.99495	61.66	0.18432	0.99529	61.73						
0.19655	0.99563	61.70	0.21368	0.99607	61.77						
0.22201	0.99630	61.77	0.23488	0.99664	61.81						
β -Alanine											
0.06288	0.99123	59.26	0.07353	0.99245	59.31						
0.09459	0.99307	59.29	0.11234	0.99359	59.32						
0.12307	0.99391	59.34	0.14076	0.99444	59.34						
0.15450	0.99484	59.37	0.16790	0.99522	59.44						
0.18511	0.99573	59.41	0.19832	0.99611	59.43						
0.21147	0.99649	59.44	0.22037	0.99675	59.46						
DL- α -Amino-n-butyric acid											
0.02599	0.99094	76.90	0.03752	0.99124	76.86						
0.04911	0.99155	76.86	0.06668	0.99201	76.92						
0.07815	0.99232	76.85	0.09579	0.99278	76.89						
0.10785	0.99309	76.98	0.11355	0.99324	76.94						
0.12536	0.99355	76.95	0.14319	0.99401	76.98						
0.15538	0.99432	77.04	0.17320	0.99478	77.04						
L-Valine											
0.04137	0.99029	91.91	0.06399	0.99186	92.16						
0.07801	0.99223	92.10	0.08788	0.99247	92.16						
0.10649	0.99294	92.22	0.11596	0.99317	92.25						
0.12878	0.99348	92.30	0.14617	0.99390	92.29						
0.16226	0.99432	92.26	0.18385	0.99484	92.32						
0.20150	0.99526	92.40									
L-Leucine											
0.03069	0.99094	109.41	0.04453	0.99124	109.48						
0.05836	0.99155	109.50	0.07911	0.99201	109.49						
0.09303	0.99278	109.49	0.10690	0.99263	109.48						
0.11348	0.99278	109.47	0.12119	0.99294	109.54						

various thermodynamic investigations^{3-6,14,21,22, 28,30-36} on amino acids in aqueous solutions, the unique hydration characteristics of these solutes have been reported as follows : (a) $^+NH_3$ and CO_2^- terminals in these solutes are hydrated in an electrostrictive manner, whereas, the intervening backbone is hydrated as per its nature which may be hydrophilic, hydrophobic or amphiphilic, (b) electrostriction of $^+NH_3$ group is greater than that of CO_2^- group by about a factor of 10 and (c) the overlap of hydration cospheres of terminal ($^+NH_3$ and CO_2^- groups) and of the groups adjacent to them results in a volume change. An increase in $\bar{V}_2^0$ occurs due to reduction in the electrostriction at the terminals whereas the decrease occurs due to the disruption of side-group hydration by that of the charged end. But the presence of side-chain also modulates the hydration cosphere of the charged ends depending on the size, shape and charge of side-chain.

Table 2. Partial molal volumes ($\bar{V}_2^0$, cm³ mol⁻¹) at infinite dilution of some amino acids in water at various temperatures*

288.15 K	298.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	318.15 K	328.15 K
42.48 ^g , 42.40 ⁱ	43.24 ± 0.04 ^a , (1.17 ± 0.18) 43.20 ^b , 43.19 ^c , 43.14 ^d , 43.22 ^e , 43.26 ^f , 43.30 ^f 43.33 ⁱ	43.79 ± 0.02 ^a , (0.86 ± 0.09) 43.79 ^c , 43.80 ^f , 44.90 ^f	Glycine 44.00 ^b , 44.15 ^c , 44.01 ^g , 43.90 ⁱ	44.17 ± 0.03 ^a (1.77 ± 0.21)	44.25 ± 0.08 ^{a,m} , (2.22 ± 1.08) 44.20 ^b , 44.51 ^g 44.30 ⁱ
59.67 ^g , 59.90 ⁱ	60.49 ± 0.05 ^a (0.77 ± 0.15) 60.50 ^c , 60.62 ^d , 60.40 ^f , 60.45 ^f , 60.47 ^g	61.01 ± 0.01 ^a , (0.83 ± 0.05) 60.9 ⁱ	DL-Alanine 61.2 ⁱ , 61.14 ^g	61.31 ± 0.04 ^a (2.09 ± 0.23)	61.60 ⁱ , 61.53 ^g
74.67 ^h	58.37 ± 0.05 ^a , (0.86 ± 0.25) 58.30 ^b , 58.63 ⁱ	58.85 ± 0.02 ^a (1.02 ± 0.11)	β-Alanine 59.10 ^b	59.19 ± 0.03 ^a (1.21 ± 0.22)	59.20 ^b
90.08 ^g	76.35 ± 0.06 ^a , (2.29 ± 0.38) 75.92 ^d , 75.51 ^h	76.61 ± 0.08 ^a (1.77 ± 0.53)	DL-α-Amino-n-butyric acid 76.34 ^h	76.82 ± 0.05 ^a (1.21 ± 0.43)	77.01 ^h
106.81 ^f	90.98 ± 0.05 ^a , (2.45 ± 0.38) 90.78 ^c , 90.98 ^d , 90.80 ^f , 90.91 ⁱ	91.55 ± 0.05 ^a (1.54 ± 0.38)	L-Valine 91.67 ^f	91.93 ± 0.10 ^a (2.34 ± 0.75)	92.57 ^f
104.90 ^f	107.77 ± 0.08 ^a , (2.93 ± 0.16) 107.74 ^c , 107.96 ^d , 107.73 ^f	108.41 ± 0.06 ^a (1.93 ± 0.54)	L-Leucine 109.00 ^f	109.38 ± 0.06 ^a (1.33 ± 0.57)	110.18 ^f
120.30 ⁱ	105.79 ± 0.14 ^a , (1.61 ± 0.70) 105.76 ^f	106.47 ± 0.11 ^a (2.31 ± 1.03)	L-Isoleucine 107.04 ^f	107.42 ± 0.05 ^a (0.89 ± 0.39)	108.09 ^f
59.70 ^g , 59.80 ⁱ	121.32 ± 0.09 ^a , (4.80 ± 3.59) 121.48 ^c , 121.70 ⁱ	122.82 ± 0.04 ^a (10.13 ± 1.81)	L-Phenylalanine 123.5 ⁱ	123.75 ± 0.002 ^a (10.30 ± 1.64)	124.90 ⁱ
76.18 ^g	60.60 ± 0.04 ^a , (0.73 ± 0.18) 60.66 ^g , 60.80 ⁱ , 60.57 ⁱ	61.15 ± 0.02 ^a (0.81 ± 0.15)	L-Serine 61.63 ^g , 61.70 ⁱ	61.86 ± 0.06 ^a (2.26 ± 0.46)	62.22 ^g , 62.20 ⁱ
88.52 ^h	76.88 ± 0.04 ^a , (0.88 ± 0.15) 76.90 ^g , 78.00 ⁱ	77.49 ± 0.04 ^a (1.02 ± 0.21)	L-Threonine 77.93 ^g	78.24 ± 0.06 ^a (0.67 ± 0.78)	78.52 ^g
	82.61 ± 0.06 ^a , (1.33 ± 0.37) 82.83 ^c , 82.50 ⁱ	83.10 ± 0.03 ^a (1.52 ± 0.25)	L-Proline 83.60 ⁱ	83.88 ± 0.03 ^a (1.60 ± 0.22)	84.50 ⁱ
	89.64 ± 0.14 ^a , (5.34 ± 2.45) 85.88 ^c , 90.06 ^h	90.60 ± 0.08 ^a (2.18 ± 0.25)	L-Glutamic acid 91.62 ^h	91.30 ± 0.05 ^a (5.84 ± 1.10)	92.84 ^h

*Parenthesis contain S_V values; ^aThis work, ^bRef. 11, ^cRef. 28, ^dRef. 31, ^eRef. 29, ^fRef. 17, ^gRef. 16, ^hRef. 20, ⁱRef. 4, ^jRef. 22, ^kRef. 30, ^lRef. 21, ^mDetermined presently.

On comparing $\bar{V}_2^0$ values, it may be seen from Table 2 that $\bar{V}_2^0$ values for the amino acids with apolar side-chains (with small variation for β-alanine and L-isoleucine) increase with size of the side-chain which have also contributions from its shielding and hydrophobic effects. Whereas in case of amino acids with hydrophilic side chains the $\bar{V}_2^0$ values are comparatively smaller than the amino acids

with apolar side-chains having corresponding number of carbon atoms particularly at lower temperatures, which may be due to the electrostriction of the water molecules. For example, L-glutamic acid and L-valine which possess the same number of carbon atoms in the side-chain, the $\bar{V}_2^0$ value is less in case of former than latter due to the presence of hydrophilic side-chain. Further, $\bar{V}_2^0$ values

depend on the location of polar group in the side-chain. It may also be seen from the data of DL-alanine and L-serine, and L-valine and L-glutamic acid that the temperature-dependence is more for amino acids with hydrophilic side-chains which indicates about their thermolabile nature of interactions.

The $\bar{V}_2^0$ values provide the information about solute-solvent interactions and molality dependence of ϕ_v will give an insight into the solute-solute interactions¹⁸. Following the approach of McMillan-Mayer Theory^{37,38}, the parameter S_v (volumetric coefficient) can characterise the pairwise interaction of solvated solute species in aqueous solution³⁹ which can be explained by considering cosphere-overlap model. For zwitterionic amino acids studied presently, the S_v values will be the resultant of contributions from the overlap of hydrophobic-hydrophobic, hydrophobic-hydrophilic and hydrophilic-hydrophilic cospheres of the solutes. The positive S_v values (Table 2) in all the cases suggest the dominance of the overlap of hydration cospheres of the $^+NH_3$ and CO_2^- groups because the interactions between charged end-groups of amino acids, i.e. $^+NH_3$ and CO_2^- , accompany positive volume change as some electrostricted water (water attached strongly to the charged end-groups) returns to the bulk water which has higher volume contribution than electrostricted water. Although the effect of these interactions dominates but the side-chain may also contribute to the molality dependence of ϕ_v and thus it will alter the value of S_v ^{35,40}.

$(\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_P$ (partial molal expansibility) and $(\partial^2\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_P$ values : The evaluation of precise values of $(\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_P$ and $(\partial^2\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_P$ requires accurate values of $\bar{V}_2^0$ at large number of temperatures^{18,23}. Therefore, in order to combine the present (at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K) and available literature (at 288.15, 313.15 and 328.15 K) $\bar{V}_2^0$ values (Table 2), the two sets of data were plotted on the same graph ($\bar{V}_2^0$ vs temperature) and smooth lines were obtained (plots not shown) which permit the use of $\bar{V}_2^0$ values at the six temperatures to estimate the above parameters. The data have been fitted using the method of least-squares into the equation similar to that used by Chalikian *et al.*¹¹,

$$\bar{V}_2^0 = a + bT + cT^2 \quad (3)$$

where a , b and c are constants and T is the temperature. Values of $(\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_P$ and $(\partial^2\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_P$ have been obtained by differentiating the above equation and the values are summarized in Table 3. The values of the above parameters have also been estimated by fitting $\bar{V}_2^0$ data into Taylor Series as reported by Kishore *et al.*⁴¹ as follows :

$$\bar{V}_2^0 = \bar{V}_2^0(298.15 \text{ K}) + (\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_P(T-298.15 \text{ K}) + 1/2 (\partial^2\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_P(T-298.15 \text{ K})^2 \quad (4)$$

The values calculated from eqn. (4) are also included in Table 3. Values of the above parameters obtained from these equations agree very well. However, for examining temperature dependence of $(\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_P$ eqn. (3) has been used. Values of $(\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_P$ decrease with the increase of temperature in all the cases studied presently except in case of L-proline where slight increase has been observed (0.061 to 0.068 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$ in the temperature range 298.15–328.15 K). Literature values of $(\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_P$ reported by Cabani *et al.*²¹ for glycine, DL-alanine, β -alanine, DL- α -amino-n-butyric acid, L-valine, L-serine and L-threonine have been compared with the present values (Table 3) and the values for glycine (0.100 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) is quite different from our value (0.063 $\pm$.009 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$). But our value is in good agreement with the value reported by Chalikian *et al.*¹¹ (0.068 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$), and thus the value reported by Cabani *et al.*²¹ seems to be in error. Similarly, the values reported by Cabani *et al.*²¹ for other compounds are consistently slightly higher than the present values (except for DL- α -amino-n-butyric acid). The value reported by Iqbal and Mateeullah²² for glycine (0.18 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) is also much higher which is associated with large uncertainty as mentioned by them because the value has been estimated from the values of $\bar{V}_2^0$ at two temperatures only.

Hepler⁴² proposed a method by which qualitative information on hydration of solutes could be obtained from the thermal expansion of aqueous solutions by using the thermodynamic relation,

$$(\partial\bar{C}_{p,2}/\partial P)_T = -T(\partial^2\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_P \quad (5)$$

It has been suggested that for a structure-breaking solute, left-side of eqn. (5) should be positive and therefore structure-breaking solutes should have negative $(\partial^2\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_P$ and similar reasoning leads to the result that positive $(\partial^2\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_P$ should be associated with the structure-making solutes. Although this qualitative classification has its limitations, even then this equation is useful for making the distinction between ionic or polar solutes and those for which hydrophobic hydration is dominant^{23,42,43}. Presently obtained $(\partial^2\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_P$ values are negative for all the amino acids except L-proline which suggests that these solutes are structure-breakers whereas L-proline having positive value seems to be structure-making solute. Therefore, the negative values of $(\partial^2\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_P$ are consistent with the dominance of ionic $^+NH_3$ and CO_2^- functional groups in solute-water interactions in all the amino acids studied except in case of L-proline where positive value of $(\partial^2\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_P$ indicate that hydrophobic interactions are dominating.

Partial molal isothermal compressibility ($K_{T,2}^0$) : Although, partial molal volume is a useful property, but it has limitation that the contribution to $\bar{V}_2^0$ arising from solute-

solvent interactions is much smaller than that arising from intrinsic volume of the molecule^{19,23}. In other words, $\bar{V}_2^0$ itself is not a particular sensitive measure of solute-solvent interactions. As the intrinsic volume of the solute should be independent of pressure at least to the first approximation, a determination of the pressure dependence of $\bar{V}_2^0$ may be useful means to characterise structural hydration effects in aqueous solution. This is a more sensitive parameter as it is a second derivative of free energy. The accurate and precise determination of pressure dependence of $\bar{V}_2^0$ is not an easy task¹⁹. However, partial molal adiabatic compressibility ($K_{s,2}^0 = -(\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_s$) can be easily determined from the velocity of sound through the solution^{19,23,44}. But partial molal isothermal compressibility ($K_{T,2}^0$) is the ideal parameter to interpret solute-solvent interactions which can be obtained from $K_{s,2}^0$ values if the partial molal expansibilities are available along with the partial molal heat capacities using the relation⁴⁵,

$$K_{T,2}^0 = K_{s,2}^0 + S_0 (2E_2^0/\alpha_0 - \bar{C}_{p,2}^0/\sigma_0) \quad (6)$$

where $E_2^0 = (\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_p$ and $\bar{C}_{p,2}^0$ are partial molal expansibility and heat capacity of the solute at infinite dilution, S_0 is the difference between the isothermal and isentropic compressibilities ($K_{T,0} - K_{s,0}$), α_0 and σ_0 are coefficients of thermal expansion and heat capacity per unit volume. The values of S_0 , α_0 and σ_0 for water at 298.15 K are $4.726 \times 10^{-12} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$, $2.55 \times 10^{-4} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $4.1720 \times 10^6 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-3}$ respectively⁴³.

The $K_{T,2}^0$ values using eqn. (6) have been calculated from partial molal expansibility coefficients ($E_2^0 = (\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_p$, determined presently), and $\bar{C}_{p,2}^0$ and $K_{s,2}^0$ values at infinite dilution (taken from literature⁴⁶). These values are summarized in Table 3. The $K_{T,2}^0$ values are available in literature only for glycine, DL-alanine, β -alanine and L-valine at 298.15 K^{21,47}. The $K_{T,2}^0$ values reported by Cabani *et al.*²¹ for these compounds are lower than that of ours and the difference for glycine is small whereas for other compounds it is large. One of the reasons for this is that $K_{s,2}^0$ values which they used are also different and they have mentioned that no satisfactory agreement exists between their and literature values. In this paper the $K_{s,2}^0$ values reported by Iqbal and Verrall⁴⁶ (reported by various authors) have been used. Secondly, their values of $(\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_p$ are also slightly different from our results. The magnitude of $K_{T,2}^0$ is a measure of the extent of hydration of solute molecules⁴⁸. The large negative values of $K_{T,2}^0$ indicate that the solute molecules are highly hydrated and small positive values indicate that solute molecules are slightly hydrated. The comparison of $K_{T,2}^0$ values for the studied amino acids suggests that L-proline is relatively less hydrated.

Hydration numbers (n_H) : The hydration numbers (Table 3) for the amino acids have been calculated using $K_{T,2}^0$ values from the following relation similar to that reported by Millero *et al.*²⁸,

$$n_H = K_{T,2}^0 (\text{amino acid}) / (K_{T,2}^0 V_B^0) \quad (7)$$

where $K_{T,2}^0$ and V_B^0 are the compressibility and molar volume of pure water. n_H values calculated from the $K_{s,2}^0$ values reported in literature²⁸ are also included in Table 3. It may be seen that the present n_H values are consistently slightly less due to smaller values of $K_{T,2}^0$ than $K_{s,2}^0$. Higher hydration number suggests that the molecule is highly hydrated

Table 3. Values of $(\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_p$, $(\partial^2\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_p$, $K_{s,2}^0$, $\bar{C}_{p,2}^0$, $K_{T,2}^0$ and n_H of various amino acids in water at 298.15 K

$(\partial\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T)_p$ cm ³ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	$(\partial^2\bar{V}_2^0/\partial T^2)_p$ cm ⁶ mol ⁻² K ⁻²	$K_{s,2}^0 \times 10^{15}$ m ³ mol ⁻¹ Pa ⁻¹	$\bar{C}_{p,2}^0$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$K_{T,2}^0 \times 10^{15}$ m ³ mol ⁻¹ Pa ⁻¹	n_H
Glycine					
0.063 ± 0.009 (0.06)	-0.0017 (-0.0020)	-27.00 ± 0.2	42.9 ± 1 ^d	-23.37 ± 0.67 -21.40 ^e	3.02, 3.34 ^c
0.100 ^f				-20.80 ^e	
DL-Alanine					
0.062 ± 0.012 (0.064)	-0.0016 (-0.0021)	-25.50 ± 0.5	146.1 ± 1 ^d	-23.37 ± 0.67 -18.50 ^e	2.86, 3.09 ^c
0.088 ^f					
β-Alanine					
0.059 ± 0.015 (0.065)	-0.0020 (-0.0025)	-26.36 ± 0.11 ^b	76.0 ± 2 ^d	-24.26 ± 0.57 -18.30 ^e	2.97
0.089 ^f					
DL-α-Aminon-butyrac acid					
0.77 ± 0.029 (0.080)	-0.0027 (-0.0047)	-	234.1 ± 3 ^d	-	-
0.76 ^f					
L-Valine					
0.66 ± 0.008 (0.066)	-0.0007 (-0.0012)	-30.62 ± 0.13	307.5 ± 3 ^d	-28.52 ± 0.32 -21.40 ^e	3.48, 3.78 ^c
0.080 ^f					
L-Leucine					
0.084 ± 0.005 (0.084)	-0.0001 (-0.0003)	-31.78 ± 0.56	402.4 ± 2 ^d	-29.12 ± 0.59	3.56, 3.93 ^c
L-Isoleucine					
0.084 ± 0.005 (0.084)	-0.0003 (-0.0005)	-31.78 ± 0.16	394.6 ± 1 ^d	-29.11 ± 0.24	3.56
L-Phenylalanine					
0.125 ± 0.011 (0.127)	-0.0008 (-0.0003)	-34.54 ± 1.48	391.0 ± 2 ^d	-30.35 ± 1.54	3.71, 4.28
L-Serine					
0.075 ± 0.010 (0.078)	-0.0012 (-0.0016)	-29.88 ± 0.10	117.4 ± 3 ^d	-27.23 ± 0.38	3.33
0.080 ^f					
L-Threonine					
0.070 ± 0.009 (0.072)	-0.0009 (-0.0010)	-31.23 ± 0.10	214.8 ± 1 ^d	-28.88 ± 0.35	3.53
0.079 ^f					
L-Proline					
0.06 ± 0.007 (0.059)	+0.0002 (0.0003)	-23.25 ± 0.11	177.1 ± 2 ^d	-21.19 ± 0.28	2.59, 2.87 ^c
L-Glutamic acid					
0.127 ± 0.024 (0.132)	-0.0032 (-0.0044)	-36.17 ± 0.38	185.2 ± 1 ^d	-31.67 ± 0.97	3.87, 4.48 ^c

*Values estimated from eqn. 4 in parenthesis; ^aRef. 47, ^bRef. 11, ^cRef. 28, ^dRef. 10, ^eRef. 21.

and hence less compressible and vice-versa. Hydration number of glutamic acid is higher relative to other amino acids, which may be attributed to the presence of charged side-chain. Smaller value of n_H in case of L-proline may again be attributed to its cyclic structure which is responsible for the smaller amount of water in the electrostricted state and therefore the negative contribution to compressibility will be less.

Experimental

Glycine, DL-alanine, DL- α -amino-n-butyric acid, L-valine, L-proline, L-leucine, L-isoleucine, L-threonine and L-phenylalanine (all Sigma), β -alanine (Sisco), L-serine (Merck) and L-glutamic acid (Eastman Org. Chem. Co.) were used as such, however, before use these were dried over P_2O_5 in a vacuum desiccator for 72 h. Water used for making solutions was deionized, doubly glass-distilled and degassed by boiling. All solutions were made on weight basis.

Density was determined with the help of a single-stem pycnometer. The temperature control of the thermostat bath used was within ± 0.01 K. Pycnometer was calibrated with water²⁴ and its working was tested by determining densities of aqueous sodium chloride solutions which agreed well with the literature values²⁵⁻²⁷. Careful measurements provided densities accurate to $0.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$.

References

1. T. H. Lilley in "Biochemical Thermodynamics", ed. M. N. Jones, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1988.
2. F. Franks in Ref. 1.
3. D. P. Kharakoz, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, **95**, 5634.
4. D. P. Kharakoz, *Biophys. Chem.*, 1989, **34**, 115.
5. G. R. Hedwig and H. Hoiland, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1991, **23**, 1029.
6. G. R. Hedwig and H. Hoiland, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1993, **25**, 349.
7. G. R. Hedwig, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1993, 2761.
8. M. Sahayam and G. R. Hedwig, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1994, **26**, 361.
9. G. I. Makhatazde and P. L. Privalov, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 1990, **213**, 375.
10. R. Bhat and J. C. Ahluwalia, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1985, **89**, 1099.
11. T. V. Chalikian, A. P. Sarvazyan and K. J. Breslauer, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1993, **97**, 13017.
12. S. Roth, *Ann. Rev. Pharmacol. Toxicol.*, 1979, **19**, 1959.
13. N. P. Frank and W. R. Leib, *Nature (London)*, 1981, **292**, 248.
14. M. Iqbal and T. Ahmed, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 119.
15. H. Zhao, A. G. Wood, F. Widdel and M. P. Bryant, *J. Bacteriol.*, 1990, **172**, 3959.
16. A. W. Hakin, M. M. Duke, S. A. Klassen, R. M. Mickay and K. E. Preuss, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1994, **72**, 362.
17. M. M. Duke, A. W. Hakin, R. M. Mickay and K. E. Preuss, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1994, **72**, 1489.
18. J. F. Reading, I. D. Watson and G. R. Hedwig, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1990, **22**, 159.
19. H. Hoiland in "Thermodynamic Data for Biochemistry and Biotechnology", ed. H. -J. Hinz, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1986.
20. A. W. Hakin, M. M. Duke, J. L. Marty and K. E. Preuss, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1994, 2027.
21. S. Cabani, G. Conti, E. Matteoli and M. R. Tine, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1981, **77**, 2377, 2385.
22. M. Iqbal and M. M. Mateeullah, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1990, **68**, 725.
23. G. R. Hedwig, J. D. Hastie and H. Hoiland, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1996, **25**, 615.
24. G. S. Kell, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1975, **20**, 97.
25. F. Vaslowf, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 2286.
26. J. E. Desnoyers, M. Arel, G. Perronad and O. Jolicoeur, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, **73**, 3346.
27. F. J. Millero, *Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **71**, 147.
28. F. J. Millero, A. L. Surdo and C. Shin, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **82**, 784.
29. B. S. Lark and K. Bala, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 192.
30. M. Iqbal and R. E. Verrall, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1987, **91**, 967.
31. G. Dipaola and B. Belleau, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1978, **56**, 1827.
32. E. J. Cohn and T. J. Edsall, "Proteins, Amino Acids and Peptides", Hafner, New York, 1965.
33. C. Jolicoeur and J. Boilieu, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1978, **56**, 2707.
34. F. Shahidi and P. G. Farrell, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1981, 963.
35. A. K. Mishra and J. C. Ahluwalia, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, **88**, 86.
36. F. Shahidi and P. G. Farrell, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1978, **74**, 858.
37. J. J. Koak, W. S. Knight and W. Kauzmann, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **48**, 675.
38. W. G. McMillan and J. E. Mayer, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, **13**, 276.
39. T. E. Leslie and T. H. Lilley, *Biopolymers*, 1985, **24**, 695.
40. J. F. Reading and G. R. Hedwig, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1989, **18**, 159.
41. N. Kishore, R. N. Goldberg and Y. B. Tewari, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1993, **25**, 847.
42. L. G. Hepler, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 4613.
43. P. J. Bernal and W. A. van Hook, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1986, **18**, 955.
44. T. S. Banipal and G. Sehgal, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1995, **262**, 175.
45. J. E. Desnoyers and P. R. Philip, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1972, **50**, 1094.
46. M. Iqbal and R. E. Verrall, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1988, **263**, 4159.
47. A. A. Yayanos, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1993, **97**, 13027.
48. A. L. Surdo, C. Shin and F. J. Millero, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1978, **23**, 197.